

benefits of promoting linguistic awareness and inclusivity outweigh these challenges. By incorporating interactive teaching strategies, providing age-appropriate resources, and offering professional support, educators can equip students with the tools they need to appreciate and navigate linguistic diversity. Ultimately, integrating sociolinguistic variation into early education helps students understand language as a vital tool for communication, identity, and engagement in a diverse world.

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USING EFFECTIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNIQUES IN TEACHING WRITING SKILLS IN THE CLASSROOM.

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***Abstract.** This article highlights the most effective ways of teaching writing through using different strategies in classroom atmosphere. This paper explain deeply about keep reading, practice storytelling, build vocabulary, differ point of view, play the word choice and structure. Overall, this article provides crucial*

background information based on writing development to improve effectiveness of writing at all.

Key words. *Writing skill, classroom atmosphere, practice story telling, build vocabulary, toolboxes, point of view, word choice and structures.*

Introduction. Writing abilities are vital in all facets of our lives. Moreover, there are lots of students in the world, they cannot neglect the writing part. As it helps in building confidence, strengthen academic achievement, finding the better job and many more things. Writing is important to express ourselves effectively in the corporate world also to develop in communication skills, getting promotion in any sphere as well. If the person has well-developed writing skill, then that one can look forward to various jobs available such as Freelance content writing, graphic designer, being great writer, editor and etc. Generally, it is so essential for composing essays, research papers and assignments that demonstrate a student's understanding of a subject. In addition to earning better grades, well-written papers demonstrate a student's breadth of knowledge and capacity for critical thought.

Writing is a skill that belongs to productive skill (Harmer,2007:265) as cited by Ihda M.Saifullah,2017.It means that the production of the language is in speaking

and written form. The people often use the language to some purpose in communication. As stated by (Richards &Renandya, 2002:303) as cited by Novi Yulianti, 2014, writing is the most difficult among the four language skills in learning foreign language. There are plenty of most beneficial strategies to teach writing in classroom.

1. Keep reading -Writing every day is important. Because, it simply improves learners writing. Note that this does not happen in a day. With constant practice and effort, it happens gradually. As time passes, regular practice will show its real effect in academic achievement. Writing for approximately 1 or 2 hours can change overall level in writing but it will be within 1 day, If writing become one of

the essential part of one's daily schedule, that person can reach positive achievement more than he expected.

2. Practice story-telling. Almost all stories have a beginning, a middle and an end. Students need to practice telling stories, whether in writing or verbally, to grasp the idea of sequencing events and the basics of story elements. Story retelling offers clear guidance on improving summarization abilities.

3. Build vocabulary-It sounds simple enough, but help students be aware of words to boost vocabulary acquisition. Emphasize when someone else uses a deliberate word choice. Encourage them to play with words. It is very significant to encourage students to keep personal dictionaries, where they that intrigue them. A thesaurus can be a budding writer's best ally in written work.

4. Building up toolboxes-it is very useful for students to begin to develop their own writer's toolbox. These toolboxes can catalog story elements such as plot, setting, character, point of view and conflict. Students can add definition and examples of literary and poetic devices such as irony, alliteration, metaphors, hyperbole and oxymoron. These strategies will give them the confidence to employ symbolism and figurative language to set their writing and prose apart from others.

5. Learning with the help of word choice and structure - Playing with words comes down to personal word choice as well as word structure. Encourage your pupils to experiment with word choice and arrangement to transform a straightforward statement.

Survey report: "Encouraging writing practice in classroom.

This study employed an online survey via a poll in the Telegram platform to collect data. A survey collects information from a small group of people in order to generalize the result to a larger population. In this survey we can know the amount of students in UzSWLU which are really interest in writing and analyze their knowledge in this point.

Findings:

1. What skill do you find the most difficult in English? (Writing 46%, Reading 28%, Speaking 26%)

2. Which factor is the most important to be master in writing? (Lexical Resource 80%, Imitate well-known writer's writing style 20%)

3. How can you rate your ability in writing? (Good 57%, Excellent 33%)

4. Which factors are the most significant to get high band score in writing? (Well-organized structure 75%, Clear ideas 25%)

The survey findings express different approaches and structure employed by learners in encouraging writing skill and creating enjoyable writing environment in the classroom. Overall, the survey analyzed total student's interests towards writing and aimed to promote students of UzSWLU to engage writing abilities.

Conclusion. Generally, the all of strategies that we mentioned above such as keep writing practice storytelling, build up vocabulary, toolboxes, using word choice and structure during writing in the classroom find the most important and beneficial by students of Uzbekistan State World Language university. These tips and tricks will promote and help them to achieve higher level in writing section to find the lucrative job or gain great result in academic competition and examinations too.

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